

Autonomous Robotic Aid For increasing First responders efficiency

D7.1: Project Web presence

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Executive summary

This deliverable, D7.1, provides an overview of the TRIFFID project's web presence and communication activities from the project's inception up to M03. It details the development of the project's website and social media platforms, which are necessary tools for disseminating information, engaging with stakeholders, and increasing the project's visibility. The deliverable also presents the project logo, which will be consistently used across all communication platforms, including the website and social media, to enhance the project's visibility and brand identity.

The TRIFFID's dissemination tracker is also introduced, which is designed to monitor the progress of communication and dissemination efforts across all partners. This tool will be instrumental in tracking the performance of the social media channels and website, providing insights into areas where further effort is needed to achieve the defined Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). In addition, this deliverable outlines the actions that the partners in WP7 will undertake to contribute to the achievement of the project's communication goals/KPIs.

Looking ahead, the next deliverable, D7.2 'Dissemination, communication, and community building 1' (M12), will provide detailed statistics on the performance of the social media platforms and website, including follower growth and other KPIs, offering a clearer picture of the project's communication impact.

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Explanation
AMR	Autonomous Mobile Robots
CP	Civil Protection
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association
FR	First Responders
GA	Grant Agreement
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
TRIFFID	auTonomous Robotic aId For increasing FIrst responDers efficiency

1. Introduction

The introduction section provides an overview of the purpose and structure of the document. It outlines the objectives and goals of the deliverable and offers a brief explanation of the document's structure. The following section will delve into the specific purpose of the document.

The purpose of this document is to provide an overview of the web presence and communication activities of the TRIFFID project up to M03. This deliverable outlines the actions and progress made regarding the project's website and social media channels, showcasing the project's visibility and engagement with its target audiences. It also provides a detailed description of the website pages and the social media profiles established for the project, highlighting how they contribute to promoting the project's objectives. Additionally, D7.1 includes an assessment of the performance tracking mechanisms in place to monitor the progress of KPIs (Key Performance Indicators), enabling the identification of areas that require additional effort to successfully achieve the project's communication goals. Finally, the document outlines conclusions, next steps and necessary actions that should be taken to ensure continued progress toward the KPIs.

This document is organized as follows:

Section 1: Presents the purpose of the document, setting the stage for the following sections.

Section 2: Provides details regarding the web presence of the TRIFFID project, including the social media platforms and website that have been developed. It also covers the KPIs of the project and the actions performed in the first three months under WP7, focusing on the progress made in communication activities.

Section 3: Describes the role of each partner in the communication activities aimed at enhancing the awareness of the project. This section highlights how the efforts of the various partners contribute to the visibility and outreach of TRIFFID.

Section 4: Summarizes the conclusions drawn from the deliverable, discusses the actions that should be undertaken, and outlines the next steps required to continue the progress of communication activities and achieve the project's KPIs.

2. Project Web presence

The TRIFFID project's Web presence is an essential component of its communication and dissemination strategy, aimed at establishing a strong online identity and engaging a broad range of audiences. To ensure effective communication and a broad dissemination, diverse communication channels will be utilized to increase awareness and foster connections with the general public as well as with relevant scientific and technical communities.

2.1. Communication channels

The TRIFFID project will carry out a range of communication activities to showcase the EC's funding for cutting-edge research, promote science as a positive and inclusive force, recruit people from all backgrounds to scientific disciplines, and enhance public knowledge of disaster response and preparedness. TRIFFID will utilize the following communication channels in order to achieve these goals:

- **Project logo, Website and visual identity:** Create an identifiable brand and a consistent digital presence by developing a logo, website, and visual identity.
- **Promotional materials, tutorials and videos:** Provide accessible and compelling content, such as flyers, brochures, and videos, to successfully reach and inform a large audience.
- **Press/Media:** Increase public awareness with focused outreach, such as press releases, interviews, and articles, to efficiently communicate project updates and accomplishments to a large audience.
- **Joining existing stakeholder communities, initiatives, DIHs and ecosystems:** Leverage the consortium's connections with stakeholders and industry networks to enhance dissemination efforts and foster collaboration beyond the AMR, FR, and civil protection sectors.
- **Social media:** The project will actively manage profiles on platforms such as LinkedIn, X (formerly known as Twitter), and Facebook, regularly publishing project findings and updates to engage a wide range of audiences.
- **Exhibitions/workshops:** TRIFFID will attend national and international events, such as exhibitions and workshops, to connect directly with key stakeholders, including specific sessions for the media and public.
- **Community building:** Expand the network of stakeholders from diverse disciplines, both directly related to the project and beyond, to facilitate networking and dissemination activities
- **Outreach/public events:** Host public events and seminars, as well as outreach sessions, to educate the general public about the project's goals, outcomes, and methods.
- **Citizen Science:** Engage the public and collaborate with the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) to enhance participation in the project.

2.1.1. Project logos

The logos of the TRIFFID project have been created to promote the project's brand recognition and provide consistent visibility across all documentation, communication, and dissemination activities. To meet the needs of diverse applications and contexts, two distinct versions of the logo have been developed: a full-scale logo (Figure 1) and a small-scale logo (Figure 2). Each has been tailored to serve

a specific purpose, enabling the TRIFFID brand to maintain a cohesive appearance across various media.

Figure 1 TRIFFID full-scale logo

Figure 2 TRIFFID small-scale logo

The project logo will be prominently featured on the project website, which will be introduced in the following section.

2.1.2. Project website

The TRIFFID’s website¹ is a tool for communicating the project's aims and progress. Its purpose is to inform visitors about the project's objectives, anticipated benefits, deployment scenarios, and major partners involved in its implementation. Additionally, the website will feature updates from the project's social media platforms, allowing visitors to be informed and up to date on the most recent news and developments. In the following, detailed descriptions and figures of the website’s pages will be provided.

2.1.2.1. Home page

Figure 3 displays the upper portion of the website's homepage, highlighting the purpose of the project and its objectives. This section is designed to provide visitors with a clear understanding of the project's mission and goals. Figure 4 showcases the social media and post updates section, enabling visitors to easily explore the latest content shared across various social media platforms. The news section includes mock posts to demonstrate their functionality, which will be detailed further in the next section. At the bottom of the page, a photo carousel showcases images of all the partners involved in the project.

¹ <https://triffid-project.eu/>

The purpose of the project

TRIFFID aims to establish a comprehensive framework for disaster risk management across Europe, integrating innovative technologies and methodologies to enhance resilience in critical infrastructures. The initiative will adopt a multi-disciplinary approach, fostering collaboration among various sectors, including emergency services, academia, and industry stakeholders. By leveraging advanced data analytics and real-time monitoring systems, TRIFFID will facilitate a proactive response to disasters, ensuring that communities are better prepared and equipped to mitigate risks associated with climate change and other emerging threats.

OUR OBJECTIVES

Objective 1

Developing an AI-Powered Hybrid UGV-UAV Platform for Remote Reconnaissance. This objective focuses on creating an autonomous hybrid platform combining Unmanned Ground Vehicles (UGVs) and Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) to enhance remote reconnaissance capabilities in disaster scenarios. The system will improve operational efficiency by minimizing human supervision through adaptive AI-powered task planning and navigation. Key goals include reducing task planning times, increasing reliability in traversing hazardous environments, ensuring compliance with safety standards, and enabling reliable, low-latency wireless communication for data exchange.

Objective 2

Enhancing Situational Awareness in Disaster Response. This objective focuses on improving robotic perception and Human-Robot Interaction (HRI) to enhance situational awareness during disaster response. The goal is to enable robots to operate safely and effectively in dynamic, hazardous environments, such as those impacted by fire, water, smoke, and collapsed buildings. Key areas include improving real-time mapping, semantic analysis of disaster scenes, gesture recognition, and sensor fusion, while ensuring the safety of humans in proximity through advanced technologies like Augmented Reality (AR).

Objective 3

Promoting Adoption of Robotic Systems in First Responder Operations. Objective 3 aims to foster the integration of AI and robotics into disaster response by establishing standards, policies, and training that support human safety, ethical guidelines, and operational efficiency. This includes ensuring ergonomic and intuitive HRI, addressing societal and psychological factors, updating protocols, and ensuring compliance with legal and ethical standards. The objective also focuses on exploring commercial opportunities derived from TRIFFID's technological innovations.

Objective 4

Development and Real-World Demonstration of TRIFFID. Objective 4 is focused on building the TRIFFID system and testing its effectiveness in real-world disaster scenarios, including fires, earthquakes, and floods. This objective involves the design and implementation of the system, followed by active involvement of first responders to tailor the system to their needs. Key goals include improving operational efficiency, reducing human exposure to danger, and ensuring the trust and acceptability of the system among users and stakeholders.

Figure 3 Homepage page 1

Latest News

Test

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamco laboris nisi ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis aute irure dolor in...

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TRIFFID Project
32 Followers
Technology, Information and internet 32 followers

[Follow Us on LinkedIn](#) [View our website](#)

TRIFFID Project
November 2024

TRIFFID Project Physical Kick-off Meeting

On November 7-8, 2024, the TRIFFID project (autonomous robots aid for increasing first responders efficiency) consortium convened at the HUA premises, in Athens, for its physical kick-off meeting, marking a key milestone in the project's 36-month journey. This two-day event brought together project partners from across Europe to discuss core objectives, strategies, and technical frameworks that will drive TRIFFID's mission.

- The meeting established essential technological strategies and collaboration goals, building a solid foundation for the project's mission: advancing innovative robotic solutions for efficient disaster response. Together, TRIFFID partners laid the groundwork for a unified approach to addressing critical disaster scenarios with cutting-edge solutions.

Stay tuned for ongoing updates as TRIFFID advances toward a more resilient future!

Follow us on our other media platforms:

- X: <https://t.me/3D3mGnQ>
- YouTube: <https://bit.ly/4BNW9RS>
- Website: <https://triffid-project.eu>

#Robotics #AI #EmergencyResponse #Innovation #EUProject

TRIFFID Project
November 2024

The TRIFFID Project (Autonomous Robotics Aid for Increasing First Responders Efficiency) Virtually Kicks Off

The TRIFFID consortium successfully convened on October 1-2, 2024, for a virtual kick-off meeting, paving the way for the upcoming physical kick-off meeting, which will take place on November 7-8, 2024, at the HUA premises in Athens!

- TRIFFID aims to enhance the efficiency of First Responders (FR) through the development of autonomous robotic solutions that will provide real-time reconnaissance in dangerous environments. The project's hybrid legged UAV-UAV platform will enable FR teams to focus on high-level decisions while reducing the need for direct human supervision in hazardous areas.
- With 13 partners from 9 European countries, including leading research institutions, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), and public safety agencies, the TRIFFID project is set to drive significant advancements in robotic solutions for disaster response.

We're excited about the future and look forward to sharing more updates as we progress!

#TRIFFIDProject #Robotics #AI #DisasterResponse #FirstResponders #Innovation #HorizonEurope #Research

Embed LinkedIn Page Posts on your WordPress website

PARTNERS

Triffid Project

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101156602.

Contact us:
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Figure 4 Homepage page 2

2.1.2.2. News page

Figure 5 depicts the news page, which breaks down into two parts, one for the blog posts created inside of the website and the other for the feeds of the project's social media pages. By clicking either on the posts or social media buttons, visitors are redirected to the relevant page, where they can stay updated with the latest blog posts (Figure 6) or social media updates (Figure 7). The blog post page currently

features placeholder posts designed to demonstrate how the content will appear once actual posts are published, while the social media page includes posts from platforms such as LinkedIn, X and others.

Figure 5 Latest news page

Figure 6 Blog posts page

Figure 7 Social media posts page

2.1.2.3. Public material page

The public material page illustrated in Figure 8, is also divided into two parts. Clicking the deliverables button redirects visitors to the project’s public repository on Zenodo², where all deliverables are readily accessible. Clicking the scientific papers button will take the visitors to a publications page, where it illustrates all the publications under the TRIFFID project, as shown in Figure 9.

² <https://zenodo.org/communities/triffid/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

Figure 8 Public material page

Figure 9 Scientific papers page

2.1.2.4. Let's connect page

Figure 10 depicts the let's connect page, which contains two spaces. The first space contains a message box that allows the visitors to send messages to the partner responsible for handling external communication, through the provision of their name and email. The second space provides links to all social media pages created for the project alongside the email, which visitors can also use to communicate.

Figure 10 Let's connect page

2.1.2.5. Pilots page

The pilots page illustrated in Figure 11, which features drop-down menus that provide detailed information for visitors. By selecting each menu, visitors can access information about the use cases, their locations, the supporting partners, the complete scenario, and the expected benefits.

Figure 11 Pilots page

2.1.2.6. About page

Figure 12 depicts the about page, which contains a paragraph that explains them in more detail. Following, a map that includes all the partners in their corresponding country of origin is depicted. Finally, at the bottom of the page, prior to the footer, there are photos of each partner alongside a button that creates a small popup window which contains information about each partner. The popup includes a brief description of each partner and their contributions to the project, as well as links to their social media pages for visitors who wish to learn more. This is depicted in Figure 13.

Figure 12 About page

Figure 13 Short description page

The other part of the dissemination will be carried out by the profiles in different social media platforms that have been created. These profiles will be used to post updates regarding the project and followers will be able to keep up to date with the project activities in real time.

2.1.3. Project social media platforms

This section provides an overview of the social media platforms established during the first month of the TRIFFID project, including LinkedIn, X (formerly Twitter), YouTube, and Facebook accounts. These platforms were created to enhance the project's visibility and raise awareness among a wide range of audiences. Each platform has a specific role in the communication plan, leveraging its unique capabilities to effectively disseminate the project's information. By strategically aligning the content shared on these platforms with their respective audiences, the TRIFFID project maximizes its outreach, ensuring its progress and that outcomes are communicated effectively with stakeholders. The role of these platforms, along with the respective accounts created on each, will be further explored in the following subsections.

2.1.3.1. Platform 'LinkedIn'

The LinkedIn page³ showcases the professional and collaborative dimensions of the TRIFFID project. It serves as a hub for professional networking, displaying key activities, and the collective efforts of the team, thus enhancing the project's presence within the professional community. Figure 14 depicts the homepage of TRIFFID's LinkedIn account.

³ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/triffid-project/>

Figure 14 TRIFFID’s LinkedIn account

2.1.3.2. Platform ‘X’

The X profile⁴ focuses on promoting the project through timely updates and highlighting upcoming events. The inclusion of the project logo and a succinct description on the profile helps in quickly engaging the audience and spread awareness about the project’s goals. Figure 15 depicts the homepage of TRIFFID’s X account.

Figure 15 TRIFFID’s X account

⁴ https://x.com/TRIFFID_PROJECT

2.1.3.3. Platform ‘YouTube’

TRIFFID’s account in YouTube⁵ is used to post videos that depict the progress and achievements of the TRIFFID project, providing a visually attractive and interactive platform to showcase the project’s technological innovations and key activities. Figure 16 illustrates the YouTube account of TRIFFID’s project.

Figure 16 TRIFFID’s YouTube account

2.1.3.4. Platform ‘Facebook’

The Facebook profile⁶ is utilized to build a community around the TRIFFID project by sharing engaging content, including posts about milestones, events, and behind-the-scenes activities. The platform provides an effective way to interact with a broader audience, encourage discussions, and promote the project's mission. Including the project logo and a comprehensive description on the profile, it ensures a professional and approachable online presence. The following Figure 17 presents the Facebook account of the TRIFFID project.

⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/@TRIFFIDPROJECT>

⁶ https://www.facebook.com/people/Triffid-Project/61569899486996/?locale=el_GR

Figure 17 TRIFFID's Facebook account

It is important to highlight that all communication activities, including social media efforts, should align with the European Commission's rules on the communication of results. The following section will provide further details on the adherence to these rules.

2.2. Adherence to the European Commission's rules on communication of results

All communication related to the project, including media relations, conferences, seminars, dissemination material such as brochures, leaflets, posters, papers, presentations, in electronic format, traditional or social media or any dissemination activities must acknowledge EC support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (Figure 18).

Figure 18 EU flag and acknowledgement of funding by the EU for the TRIFFID project (presented in project GA)

Additionally, all communications must indicate the following disclaimer, translated into local languages where applicable.

“Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe programme (grant agreement 101168042)”. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or [name of the granting authority]. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

2.3. Measuring the success of communication channels - KPIs

Table 1 illustrates the communication measures for TRIFFID, detailing the duration of their implementation and the associated KPIs for each channel. The table consists of the following columns:

- **Communication channel:** Specifies the various communication channels used by TRIFFID, such as the Project website, social media, and press/media.
- **Duration:** Indicates the time frame over which each communication channel will be implemented or actively utilized in order to achieve the desired outcomes.
- **KPIs:** Lists the KPIs for each communication channel, which are used to measure the effectiveness and success of the communication efforts.

Table 1 Communication measures

Communication channel	Duration	KPIs
Project website	M01-M36	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online presence by M03 • Unique new users per year > 2000 (M36)
Promotional materials, tutorials, and videos	M12-M36	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • YouTube total views > 5000 • Project flyers, leaflets, posters & brochures > 8
Press/Media	M12-M36	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Media articles > 20
Joining existing stakeholder communities, initiatives, DIHs and ecosystems	M01-M12 + updates	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Articles in CP, FR and disaster response magazines > 3 • Presence in industry-led conferences > 3

Social media	M12-M36	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New LinkedIn, Facebook and X followers per year >600
Exhibitions/Workshops	M12-M36	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in exhibitions, seminars and trade fairs > 3 • Organization of large public seminars for stakeholders = 2 (by HUA and DCNA) • TRIFFID Workshops = 3
Outreach/Public events	M01-M36	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public events/seminars for publication = 2

2.4. Activities performed (M01-M03)

The following activities were undertaken to establish and enhance the communication and dissemination framework of the TRIFFID project:

- **Creation of the project website:** A dedicated website was launched to serve as the central hub for project information, updates, and resources, providing accessible and comprehensive content for stakeholders and the public.
- **Social media account setup:** Official accounts were created on LinkedIn, YouTube, Facebook, and X to expand the project's digital presence and engage with diverse audiences.
- **Development of the dissemination tracker:** A dissemination tracker was developed to monitor and document the dissemination activities conducted by each partner.

The primary theme showcased on the website and social media platforms centered around the project's kick-off meeting, the first major event organized under the TRIFFID project. An initial community of followers has begun to form. To further expand awareness, each partner provided a brief description of their organization along with their social media links, which have been featured on the project's website.

Additionally, partners are informed to provide at least two weeks' notice for any planned participation in workshops, conferences, or events where TRIFFID will be presented. This advance notice ensures that there is ample time to prepare communication materials, such as social media posts and website updates. Partners are also expected to update the dissemination tracker, which is in the project's shared file, to document all dissemination activities.

2.5. Performance tracking

Performance tracking is a part of assessing the effectiveness of communication and dissemination activities. By systematically monitoring and assessing the effectiveness of these efforts, it becomes easier to ensure that the project's objectives are being achieved and its intended impact is realized. To support this process, a dissemination tracker has been developed in excel format, where partners will record and track their activities. The input provided by the partners in the dissemination tracker will be converted into tangible communication activities for the project, such as posts, articles, and promotional content, aimed at boosting the project's visibility and enhancing its overall popularity. The tracker is made available through the shared repository, ensuring that all partners have access to it. Further details about the tracker will be provided in the following subsection.

Types of audience
Scientific and Industrial Communities (AMRs, AI/machine learning, computer vision, EO, NLP, HRI, AR, legal and ethical studies, wireless communications, civil protection studies)
General Public
Policy Makers
Humanitarian and Disaster Response Organizations
Media
Others

Figure 23 TRIFFID dissemination tracker (types of audience)

Types of publications
Conference paper
Publication in Conference proceedings
Journal paper
Workshop paper
Special Issue
Book chapter
Online
Preprint
Editorial
Others (please specify)
Publication Status
Accepted publication
Submitted publication
Planned/future Publication
Others (please specify)

Figure 24 TRIFFID dissemination tracker (types of publications)

HUA
HMU
UPC
VUB
UWB
CNR
DCNA
TEL
ITML
PUI
GB
HFC
ROE

Figure 25 TRIFFID dissemination tracker (project partners)

3. Task sharing and partners' role in WP7

This section provides an overview of how partners will contribute to WP7, focusing on communication activities. The partners will provide details about their responsibilities and their contributions to the communication activities of WP7, which will be described in the following subsection.

3.1. Partners' role in communication tasks

This subsection highlights the roles and contributions of each partner in communication activities, including social media management, promotion of TRIFFID media, e-newsletters, online publishing, blogging, creation of promotional materials, and production of media such as newspaper articles and multimedia content. Table 2 outlines the responsibilities of each partner and their contributions to communication activities.

Table 2 Partners' role in communication tasks

Partner	Responsibilities	Contribution to communication activities
HUA	HUA is TRIFFID's project coordinator (T1.1) and as such will contribute to disseminating and communicating the scientific and technical outcomes of the project. Further, HUA leads WP4 and collaborates with other tasks/WPs and their results will be published in prestigious scientific journals/conferences.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific publications • Participating in conferences • HUA social media channels (LinkedIn, Facebook, X) • Blog posts for HUA's website • Organization of a large public seminar for stakeholders
HMU	The Hellenic Mediterranean University, as the task leader for T7.1 'Communication and Dissemination Activities', ensures the effective communication of TRIFFID's participation in workshops, publications, events, and conferences. HMU is responsible for communicating TRIFFID activities through the Project's website, social media, newsletters, blogs, multimedia.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project website • TRIFFID's social media channels • HMU's social media channels (LinkedIn, X) • Blogs • Promotional materials • e-Newsletter • Media • Multimedia
UPC	UPC is TRIFFID's technical manager (T1.2) and as such will contribute to disseminate and communicate the scientific and technical outcomes of the project. Further, UPC leads WP3 and collaborates to many other tasks and their results will be published in prestigious scientific journals/conferences.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific publications • Updating UPC's (IRI) social media (LinkedIn, X, Facebook) according to TRIFFID's needs (reposting & creating communication content when needed). • Blog posts for UPC's website (IRI's newsletter) • Participating in workshops • Contributing to the creation and sharing of promotional materials/media articles
VUB	Law and Ethics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • News updates on institutional website https://cdsl.research.vub.be/

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation to conferences (i.e. https://www.cpdpconferences.org/) • Publications
UWB	UWB leads T6.2 ‘Robot, Sensor, and Communication Integration’. UWB will participate in communication and dissemination activities, supporting the respective partners.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific publications • Updating UWB’s (IRI) social media (LinkedIn, Facebook) according to TRIFFID’s needs (reposting & creating communication content when needed). • Participating in workshops • Contributing to the creation and sharing of promotional materials/media articles
CNR	CNR leads T5.1 regarding human factor analysis for efficient interaction with humans. As a research partner, CNR will mainly contribute towards the scientific dissemination of the project.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific publications • Updating CNR’s social media channels. • Participating in workshops • Contributing to the creation and sharing of promotional materials/media articles
DCNA	The Disaster Competence Network Austria is responsible for T2.5 and WP5. In addition, DCNA will participate in communication and dissemination activities, supporting the respective partners and is furthermore responsible for evaluation activities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DCNA social media channels (LinkedIn, Facebook) • DCNA website and blog • Promotional materials • DCNA newsletter (for the network, mostly national level/German-speaking)
TEL	As a TRIFFID business partner, TEL will enhance its existing commercial product by exploiting the advancements of TRIFFID's disruptive technology and will actively disseminate the outcomes and acquired expertise to the targeted audience.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation and demonstration of TRIFFID to disaster-resilient society and smart city events • TRIFFID’s social media channels • Co-creation of promotional materials • Clustering with targeted stakeholders etc.
ITML	ITML is responsible for T1.5 (Innovation management), T4.2 (Non-visual data analysis and information fusion) and T7.3 (Exploitation plan and project uptake activities). At the same time, ITML contributes to many other tasks, including communication activities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updating ITML’s social media (LinkedIn, X, Facebook) according to TRIFFID’s needs (reposting & creating communication content when needed). • Blog posts for ITML’s website • Participating in workshops • Contributing to the creation and sharing of promotional materials/media articles
PUI	PUI is responsible in the TRIFFID project for contributing to the Use-Case #1: Wildfire at the Wildland–Industrial Area Interface. PUI’s tasks include defining scenario definition, pilot evaluation, and leading the planning of all pilots.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of TRIFFID to INSARAG network (60 certified international teams) • Participation and demonstration of TRIFFID to Civil Protection Society • Dissemination of TRIFFID to social media channels (FB, X, LinkedIn, Instagram) • Co-creation of promotional materials (also translated in French) • Clustering with targeted stakeholders and interested parties • Presentation of TRIFFID to EVOLSAR - European Association of 17 teams

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation to conferences (Congrès Nationale de Sapeurs Pompiers etc) • Presentation of TRIFFID to the EU projects PUI is involved with (ERASMUS+, Marie Curie, Horizon2020, Horizon Europe)
GB	GB is responsible for leading WP2: Use-case requirements and pilot studies. Additionally, GB leads T2.1 ‘End-user requirements’, T2.4 ‘Pilot execution’, and T7.2 ‘Community building and clustering with relevant activities.’	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social media posts on own channels • Participation in workshops • Contributing to the sharing of promotional materials/media articles • Clustering with relevant initiatives
HFC	HFC leads T2.2 regarding the pilot scenario definition. As an end-user partner, HFC will facilitate the dissemination of the project’s outcomes to the first responders’ community.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Media posts on own channels • Participation in workshops • Contributing to the sharing of promotional materials/media articles • Clustering with relevant initiatives
ROE	ROE is mainly involved in tasks related to user requirements definition and execution of pilots. ROE will mainly facilitate the dissemination of the project’s outcomes to the first responders’ community and respective administrative authorities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Media posts on own channels • Participation in workshops • Contributing to the sharing of promotional materials/media articles • Clustering with relevant initiatives

4. Conclusions

In conclusion, as highlighted in the previous sections, the TRIFFID project has successfully established its social media platforms, and the development of the website is now complete. It is important to note, that while the developments reflect the project's status as of M03, updates and changes are likely as the project progresses. For example, website pages may be modified, or new ones may be created to better align with the project milestones and evolving goals over its lifecycle. While improvements may be required as the project proceeds, it has now its dedicated platforms for disseminating meeting updates, technology breakthroughs, and other significant advancements. These platforms will be essential in boosting the project's awareness within various communities. Moving ahead, the emphasis will be on monitoring the partners' communication efforts and working towards the successful achievement of the defined KPIs. Efforts will be made to raise project awareness, engage increasing audience, and keep the social media platforms and website up to date with the latest news and developments. The next deliverable, D7.2 "Dissemination, communication, community building 1", due in M12, will provide detailed insights into the communication and dissemination activities of the project, including social media and website progress statistics, as well as updates on WP7 KPIs.